

RT: 0.00 - 0.44

NL:
1.93E8
bq_181_2#1 RT: 0.01
AV: 1 T: FTMS + p ESI
Full ms
[280.0000-350.0000]

NL:
8.01E5
C₁₅H₁₄FO₃S:
C₁₅H₁₄F₁O₃S₁
pa Chrg 1

NL:
8.01E5
C₁₅H₁₃FO₃S +Na:
C₁₅H₁₃F₁O₃S₁Na₁
pa Chrg 1